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The Narratives of Teachers in the Hinterland Schools: Basis for Management Plan

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Abstract

This qualitative study narrates teachers' stories and lived experiences in hinterland schools. There is a massive gap in delivering high-quality education in the hinterland for a variety of reasons, including the teachers' lack of contextualization, connections, integration of cultural values in the classroom, ignorance of IP needs, and the lack of a clear vision for their empowerment that takes into account the entire community and support network, among others. By understanding teachers' experiences in hinterland schools, policymakers and educators can create strategies to support and enhance the quality of education in these remote areas. Based on the four themes of place-based education theory, the study aims to better understand teachers' experiences in hinterland schools and identify effective strategies for supporting professional development and well-being. This study uses a qualitative research design. This study used purposive sampling as a technique in qualifying participants from Moalboal's hinterland schools. The findings revealed that teachers' perspectives on rural education are influenced by their social, personal, and professional experiences. The interaction between teachers and the community is crucial in supporting student learning. The study revealed that personal well-being, time management, and differentiated instruction could improve access to quality education for students. The study on teachers' narratives in the hinterland schools revealed a need for increased communication and collaboration between team members and a focus on developing a more positive and supportive team culture.

Keywords: *hinterland schools, rural teaching, teaching experiences in rural schools*

Introduction

Education is essential for individual growth, social mobility, and developing critical thinking skills to navigate the world's complexities. Teaching in hinterland schools, frequently in rural or remote areas, can bring unique challenges and rewards (Lisondra, 2023). Teachers in these settings may need more resources, fewer students, and isolation from urban centers (Tinampay, 2023). The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic exacerbated these challenges for teachers in rural schools, especially given the lack of virtual or modular resources in their area (Flores et al., 2023). The challenge in teaching following the pandemic is addressing the emerging learning gaps and inequalities while adapting to new technologies and pedagogical approaches in a rapidly changing educational landscape (Villar et al., 2022). Investing in teacher professional development, strengthening education systems, and expanding access to digital technologies and resources will solve teaching challenges after the pandemic (Cabello et al., 2022).

According to Murray et al. (2020), an unfavorable proportion of college graduates opt to work in the more established and prosperous coastal and urban regions, which also capture competent educators from less developed areas. In another research investigation by De Lisser & Wilkinson (2020), the findings indicated a contradiction that suggests hinterland teachers respond more favorably to an English-based language than coastland teachers. However, English speakers are more prevalent in the coastlands. There is also an issue with literacy instruction, Ministry of Education directives, and teachers' attitudes toward native and English-based languages. Regarding the lived experiences of school heads in remote area public schools, Gallego's (2022) study revealed that school officials in remote places had to deal with physical and emotional discomforts, modifications to teaching and community life, and work consolations.

Their coping techniques include teaching, engaging in physical endurance exercises, developing emotional resiliency and communal coping mechanisms, and creating a constructive workplace environment. However, in another study by Robiños et al. (2020), a shared narrative of teachers' experiences educating students in hinterland schools revealed that teachers boldly claimed to deliver a significant impact among learners, aiming to transfer understanding and make a difference. In addition, learners' diverse behaviors and learning preferences were among the common issues that encouraged teachers to adopt progressive ideology and learner-centered instruction approaches. Teachers proposed that teaching is a life-long obligation and that inclusive education is imperative.

There is a massive gap in delivering high-quality education in the hinterland for a variety of reasons, including the teachers' lack of contextualization, connections, integration of cultural values in the classroom, ignorance of IP needs, and the lack of a clear vision for their empowerment that takes into account the entire community and support network, among others. Most education systems present challenges for teachers working in remote schools (Gantalao et al., 2023). Still, these difficulties can be reduced if experiences are shared through specific professional development exchanges between teachers and the community. According to Ubalde (2009), as cited in Robiños et al. (2020), poor wages, poor working conditions, and few opportunities for teaching promotion have led to migration, which has kept teachers looking for greener pastures. Other research findings demonstrated that teachers in hinterland schools frequently encountered difficulties when attempting to improve their students' viewing and digital literacy, reading comprehension, writing skills, ability to contextualize lessons, adherence to the spiral progression in language, and instruction of orthography and grammar (Ando et al., 2022). According to the findings, these challenges were exacerbated by disparities in language learning

standards, instructional learning assistance, learners' literacy and readiness levels, and instructors' skill and methodological proficiency (Bastida et al., 2022).

Unfolding the stories of teachers' lives in hinterland schools is essential in comprehending the unique difficulties that these educators face, identifying factors contributing to teacher retention, and informing policy and practice to improve working conditions and student outcomes in these areas (Binondo et al., 2023). Teachers in rural schools frequently work in low-income neighborhoods and serve a diverse student population. Knowing these communities' and students' particular needs, like language barriers, may assist in developing effective teaching strategies to meet their needs (Zeichner & Johnson, 2015). Furthermore, a growing interest in improving educational equity necessitates a better understanding of teachers' challenges and opportunities in various contexts, including hinterland schools. These interests can lead to a more nuanced understanding of how teachers can address their student's needs and promote more equitable outcomes for all students (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

Looking into teachers' experiences in hinterland schools is a crucial area of inquiry, as these schools frequently encounter unique obstacles due to their remote settings and limited resources. Teachers encountered difficulties associated with facilities, access to resources, and limited opportunities for personal growth (Persaud & Tiwari, 2019). By understanding teachers' experiences in hinterland schools, policymakers and educators can devise strategies to support and enhance the quality of education in these remote areas.

Theoretical Underpinning

Place-based Education (PBE) theory, initially proposed at the beginning of the 1990s by Laurie Lane-Zucker of The Orion Society and Dr. John Elder of Middlebury College, serves as the theoretical framework for this study. The approach emphasizes connecting learning to the local environment and community. It also highlights the value of experiential and contextual learning and the importance of community-based problem-solving (Elfer, 2016). This theory explores how the local context and environment shape teachers' experiences in rural schools and how these experiences relate to educational policies and practices (Gruenewald, 2003). In Webber (2021)'s research study, the development of the history of PBE is based on an analysis of the streams of influence, including indigenous, outdoor, experiential, environmental, and critical education.

Place-based learning experiences link people and places with design processes and products, according to a case study by Best et al. (2017). According to the authors, place-based learning opportunities in higher education are beneficial for giving service teachers chances to advance their knowledge, awareness, and understanding of the connections between design processes and products and the requirements of people and places. According to McInerney et al.'s (2011) study, place-based education (PBE) has a place in schools. Still, it must be grounded in a much more profound comprehension of the concepts of "place," "identity," and "community." Concerning curriculum, pedagogy, and teacher preparation, the effects of implementing a place-based instruction requirement are discussed.

In a more comprehensive study conducted by Howley et al. (2011), four themes helped to explain the relevant dynamics: principal leadership, interactions with seasonal residents, instructors' diverse methods, and a school culture that encourages student inquiry. In his study, a different author detailed the context that led rise to place-based education in its present form. PBE is positioned as a cutting-edge hub for addressing the challenges educators confront in the twenty-first century (Webber, 2021).

Place-based education is the term used to describe educational approaches that deliberately attempt to link the reality of place to learning, particularly for the aim of student engagement (Azano, 2011). It incorporates the significance and experiences of the site in teaching and learning, which can go further beyond the boundaries of the school (Yemini et al., 2023). A geographical point of view may aid place-based education studies to improve their ability to promote social justice and environmental sustainability, making geographical studies education more relevant (Israel, 2012). Studies on learning environments recognize that social conditions are a part of learning and affect the quality of knowledge and experience (Zandvliet, 2012).

Using the theory of place-based education, the authors seek to explore how the experiences and perspectives of teachers in rural areas shape their understanding of education and the role of schools in their communities. The authors also want to examine how these narratives and experiences relate to broader educational policies and practices and how they inform the development of more effective education policies and techniques tailored to rural community's needs.

Research Questions

This study probes the narratives, sentiments, and lived experiences among the teachers of hinterland schools in Moalboal District, Moalboal, Cebu, for the school year 2022-2023 as the basis for a management plan. Specifically, this study uncovers the following queries:

1. What are the struggles of teachers in the hinterland schools of Moalboal District?
2. What are their sentiments, especially in transportation, accommodation, and financial obligation or capacity?
3. What are their victories and breakthroughs, the inspiring experiences they can share?
4. What is the meaning of their experiences?
5. What management plan can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Hinterland schools, also called remote or rural schools, are frequently situated far from urban centers and may need access to the same educational resources and support as schools in towns and cities. Consequently, teachers in these schools may encounter unique obstacles that hinder their capacity to instruct and engage students effectively. Inadequate resources, cultural differences, and geographical isolation are challenges teachers face in rural schools (Persaud & Tiwari, 2019).

A school's facilities and location can significantly affect teachers' job satisfaction and retention rates. Rural schools and academic institutions with inadequate facilities, such as poor ventilation systems, had higher teacher turnover rates. Benkert and Toma (2018) found that teachers were less likely to leave their positions if they worked in schools with superior amenities and in metropolitan regions. Likewise, Goldring et al. (2013) analyzed the correlation between school facilities and teacher job satisfaction in Tennessee. The study found that teachers who worked in schools with superior facilities, such as modern technology, sufficient classroom space, and clean and well-maintained buildings, were more likely to be satisfied with their jobs. Furthermore, the physical condition of school facilities was one of the strongest predictors of teacher job satisfaction.

Appropriate school facilities, such as well-maintained classrooms, comfortable workstations, and up-to-date technology, can contribute to a positive and encouraging learning environment for teachers and students. Inadequately maintained facilities can have a negative impact on teacher morale and performance. Teachers were likelier to stay at their present school if they worked at an institution with well-kept facilities (Barrera & Shear, 2017). Inadequate facilities, such as obsolete technology and poor lighting, affect teacher job satisfaction and significantly contribute to high teacher turnover rates (Gharavi & Khaleedian, 2019).

Rural or remote schools might lack access to technological advances, professional development opportunities, and specialized services (e.g., mental health services). This can impede teachers' ability to deliver their pupils with quality instruction and support (Hornbeck & Conner, 2013). Moreover, urban schools may have a broader range of student populations than their rural counterparts, posing unique challenges for educators. (e.g., language barriers, cultural differences) (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). Also, educational institutions in small towns or rural areas may have stronger ties to their local communities, allowing instructors to interact with families and community members. This can, however, put teachers under pressure to live up to societal norms and expectations (Gist & Lubinski, 2012). The expense of living in a hinterland area can affect a teacher's ability to cover housing, transportation, and other fundamental necessities. This can affect their employment satisfaction and rate of retention (Ingersoll & Perda, 2010).

Cultural norms may also impact how educators interact with kids and their families. Some cultures place a premium on forthrightness and assertiveness in conversation, while others value indirection and politeness (Chen & Starosa, 2000). Teachers who are unaware of these distinctions may misinterpret a student's behavior or misconstrue a parent's intentions. Educators unaware that some cultures emphasize memorization and rote learning while others prioritize critical thinking and problem-solving may employ ineffective teaching strategies for particular student groups (Hofstede, 2001).

Teachers are oblivious that discipline and authority are highly valued in certain societies. In contrast, collaboration and group work are preferred by others, but they may need help keeping classroom control or unintentionally offend students or their families (Gestwicki, 2010). Certain traditions may place the highest value on academic achievement, and others may regard education as a way of building interpersonal abilities and relationships. Educators who are unaware of these distinctions may fail to comprehend their students' motivations or inadvertently perpetuate cultural biases (Wang & Degol, 2016).

The Philippines faces a teacher shortage, particularly in remote and rural areas (Lincuna, 2019). Recognizing teachers' difficulties and opportunities in peripheral schools can aid policymakers and educators in developing recruitment and retention strategies and management plans. Frequently, Philippine hinterland schools need more resources, facilities, and student-teacher ratios. It may be difficult for teachers in these institutions to provide quality education to their students. A decent education should be available to all learners, regardless of where they live, as receiving an education is a fundamental human right.

Methodology

A qualitative study systematically comprehends a human problem based on the reporting informants' detailed perspectives (Cresswell, 1994). This study uses a qualitative research design. Qualitative research can also obtain information from direct participants and collect data directly (Samuels, 2011). This interview will be used to synthesize and collect teachers' subjective experiences and anecdotes while working in upland schools.

The interviewing procedure will involve using recorders and other materials that will be transcribed into a paper. After transcribing, interviewees will sign the lower right section as evidence of authenticity and to indicate that the collected data will not be revised, altered, or reanalyzed. The qualitative study is deemed suitable for this research because the objective of this study is to narrate the difficulties and lived experiences of teachers in hinterland schools. This study uses a stratagem of purposive sampling, as the respondents are instructors from Moalboal's hinterland schools.

The research team has carefully crafted their study's guiding questions. Preceding the to-be-used questions are utilized, the validators evaluate and validate them (Cabello & Bonotan, 2021). The queries will be verified and then put through a trial phase. The research

queries employed in this study are open-ended, encouraging teachers to share their experiences and perspectives. The questions are written and posed in English, and respondents may use the language they are most comfortable expressing themselves freely and without hesitation.

Results and Discussion

School Culture that Fosters Students' Inquiry

The initial portion of the inquiry focuses on the experiences, perceptions, and community interactions of school instructors in remote or sparsely populated areas, as revealed by their responses to the survey.

Table 1. School Culture that Fosters Students' Inquiry

	<i>Experiences working as a teacher in a remote school area (Q1)</i>	<i>Duties and responsibilities as a teacher in a hinterland school (Q2)</i>	<i>Instances when the role and responsibilities changed while working in hinterland schools (Q3)</i>	<i>Challenges and opportunities encountered while teaching in hinterland schools (Q4)</i>	<i>Themes</i>
					Perspectives on Rural Education
R1	Social Experiences	Classroom Management	School Setting	Making a Difference	Functions of a Rural Educator
	Personal Experiences			Building Relationships	The Influences on Teachers' Roles and Responsibilities in Rural Classrooms
					Limitations and Opportunities of Hinterland Teaching Perspectives on the Rural Education
R2	Professional Experiences	Teaching and Planning Lessons	School Setting	Limited Resources	Functions of a Rural Educator
					The Influences on Teachers' Roles and Responsibilities in Rural Classrooms
					Limitations and Opportunities of Hinterland Teaching Perspectives on the Rural Education
R3	Personal Experiences	Teaching and Planning Lessons	Student Intervention	Student Diversity	Functions of a Rural Educator
					The Influences on Teachers' Roles and Responsibilities in Rural Classrooms
					Limitations and Opportunities of Hinterland Teaching Perspectives on the Rural Education
R4	Personal Experiences	Teaching and Planning Lessons	School Setting	Teacher Shortage	Functions of a Rural Educator
				Distance and Isolation	The Influences on Teachers' Roles and Responsibilities in Rural Classrooms
				Building Relationships	Limitations and Opportunities of Hinterland Teaching
	Professional Experiences	Community Engagement			
		Professional Development			

Three categories were created for experiences teaching in remote areas (Q1), four for duties and responsibilities in hinterland schools (Q2), two for instances when roles and responsibilities changed (Q3), and six for challenges and opportunities (Q4). Four major themes emerged in the first part of the survey; perspectives on rural education, functions of a rural educator, the influences on teachers' roles

and responsibilities in rural classrooms, and limitations and opportunities of hinterland teaching.

Perspectives on Rural Education

Individuals can have different views on country education based on their experiences. Teachers' perspectives on rural education highlight the unique challenges and opportunities of teaching in rural areas. In the data gathered, three categories were created; social, personal, and professional experiences. Respondent one (R1) revealed that social and personal experiences were experienced in their school. Social experiences are experiences that teachers have in their interactions with others, including students, colleagues, parents, and community members. Social experiences may include positive experiences, such as building relationships with students and families, and negative experiences, such as conflicts with colleagues or complicated interactions with students or parents. Personal experiences are the experiences teachers have in their personal lives. They may include experiences related to their family, hobbies, and interests. Personal experiences can impact a teacher's professional life, as they may influence their teaching style, approach, and values.

Respondents two and four (R2 & R4) revealed their professional experiences. Professional experiences are experiences that teachers have related to their work as educators. They may include experiences related to teaching and learning, such as planning and delivering lessons, assessing students' progress, and collaborating with colleagues. Professional experiences may also have experiences related to professional development, such as attending conferences and workshops, completing additional training, or engaging in research or scholarly activities.

Functions of a Rural Educator

The role of a rural educator extends beyond traditional classroom instruction and encompasses a wide range of functions critical to the success of rural schools and communities. The data gathered created four categories: classroom management, teaching and planning lessons, community engagement, and professional development.

Respondent one (R1) functioned as a classroom manager. Rural educators must manage their classroom environment, including a smaller class size and fewer resources than urban or suburban schools. They may need to be creative in finding ways to engage and motivate their students and may need to be flexible in adapting their teaching methods to meet the needs of a diverse range of students.

Respondents two and three (R2 & R3) functioned as teaching and lesson planners. Teachers in remote schools are responsible for planning and delivering lessons that align with the curriculum and meet the learning needs of their students. They may need to develop innovative teaching methods and adapt their lessons to suit the limited resources available in remote area.

Respondent four (R4) included community management and professional development as his functions. Teachers in remote schools may be responsible for engaging with the local community and building relationships with families and community organizations. They may need to attend community events and participate in local initiatives to support the development of the community. In addition, teachers in remote schools are responsible for maintaining their professional knowledge and skills through ongoing professional development opportunities. They may need to seek professional development opportunities in the remote area or participate in online training programs.

The Influences on Teachers' Roles and Responsibilities in Rural Classrooms

In rural classrooms, teachers encounter distinct obstacles and frequently assume various responsibilities beyond their instructional duties, including serving as an intermediary to the community, providing counseling, and acting as a mentor. The data gathered created two categories: school setting and student intervention.

R1, R2, and R4 felt the school setting affected their duties and responsibilities as rural instructors. Rural and urban teachers have very different tasks. In smaller schools, teachers have more work. Teacher specialization depends on school size. Rural areas may need more resources. Thus, teachers may need to be more creative and work with local groups to provide kids with the necessary tools. Rural teachers face more poverty and social issues than their urban and suburban counterparts; therefore, socio-economic status matters. Teachers must be educators and advocates while assisting kids and families. Culture plays a role in shaping rural educators. Teachers must adapt their methods in culturally diverse communities to reflect community values and beliefs.

R3 believed that student intervention affected his role and duties as a teacher in a school in the hinterland. In rural areas, where resources may be limited, teachers need to figure out what their students need and help them with it. To give learners a good education, one has to test them, make personalized education plans for them, and work with their families and other experts to ensure they get the right help.

Limitations and Opportunities of Hinterland Teaching

While teaching in rural places has challenges, the chance to help students and communities is rewarding for teachers. The data collected for the inquiry was put into six categories: making a difference, building relationships, limited resources, student diversity, teacher lack, and distance and isolation.

R1 faced making a difference and building relationships as his challenges and opportunities in teaching in a hinterland school. Teaching

in schools in the country has both obstacles and chances of making a difference. Teaching in remote, rural areas can be challenging because there are fewer tools, fewer chances for professional growth, and as many trained professionals. Teachers' limits can make it hard to give the best education possible and significantly affect their students' lives. The lives of their children and their families can be profoundly influenced by the teachers who work in rural schools. In some ways, teachers' jobs go beyond the classroom. They can be guides, advocates, and a significant source of support for their students and their families. Teaching outside a city can give you more meaning and fulfillment than teaching in a town.

R2 viewed limited resources as his challenge in teaching in a hinterland school. Schools in rural areas frequently have constrained access to various resources, including computers, textbooks, and other instructional materials. Because of this, it can be challenging for educators to develop classes that are both entertaining and productive.

R3 said that student diversity is a challenge and an opportunity in his school. When there are fewer students in a rural school, there may be less language, culture, and ethnic variety. Teachers may need help to ensure that all of their student's needs are met and to set up a learning setting sensitive to different cultures. Also, it may be hard for rural schools to find and keep highly skilled teachers from diverse backgrounds. This makes it even harder for the teaching staff to have a wide range of ideas and experiences. Rural schools give teachers a chance to learn about and respect diversity. Rural areas may not have as much ethnic, cultural, and linguistic variation among students. Still, their different socioeconomic backgrounds and life experiences can make for a unique and rich classroom environment. Teachers can help students prepare for a globalized world by incorporating multicultural views and experiences into lessons. This can help students see things from a broader perspective and prepare them for a globalized world.

R4 states that teacher shortage and distance and isolation are the challenges and opportunities for a teacher in a rural area. Numerous schools located in rural locations have considerable obstacles when recruiting and retaining quality teaching staff. Students may experience more disruption when teachers have a high turnover rate. Teachers in hinterland schools may feel disconnected from the larger education community due to their remoteness and restricted collaboration and professional development options. Accessing support resources and taking part in extracurricular activities might be difficult for students attending schools in hinterland locations because of their geographical isolation.

Figure 1. Emergent Themes on School Culture that Fosters Students' Inquiry

Interactions with Seasonal Residents

The second part of the survey touch upon the challenges and benefits of working in a community with seasonal residents.

Two categories were created for the interaction with community members in creating a supportive learning environment for students (Q1), and four categories for the factors that influenced the decision to stay or leave the position as a teacher in a hinterland school(Q2). Two major themes emerged in the second part of the survey; community interaction that supports student learning and variables influencing teacher turnover in rural schools.

Table 2. *Interaction With Seasonal Residents*

	<i>Interaction with community members in creating a supportive learning environment for students (Q1)</i>	<i>Factors that influenced the decision to stay or leave the position as a teacher in a hinterland school (Q2)</i>	<i>Themes</i>
R1	Parent and Family Engagement	Transportation Compensation and Benefits	Community Interaction that Supports Student Learning Variables Influencing Teacher Turnover in Rural Schools Community Interaction that Supports Student Learning
R2	Community Engagement	Classroom Environment	Variables Influencing Teacher Turnover in Rural Schools Community Interaction that Supports Student Learning
R3	Parent and Family Engagement Community Engagement	Classroom Environment	Variables Influencing Teacher Turnover in Rural Schools Community Interaction that Supports Student Learning
R4	Parent and Family Engagement	Classroom Environment Community Support	Variables Influencing Teacher Turnover in Rural Schools

Community Interaction that Supports Student Learning

The support of student learning can be significantly enhanced through the interaction between teachers and the community. The collaborative efforts of teachers and community members can establish a conducive and stimulating educational setting that fosters academic achievement among students.

Respondents one, three, and four (R1, R3, R4) involved parent and family engagement. The involvement of parents and families in a child's education can enhance the child's motivation and engagement in school. Parents may support their children's learning by helping with schoolwork, offering educational tools, and encouraging a positive attitude toward education. This support can boost confidence and academic success. Active parental and family engagement in a student's education positively correlates with the student's perception of education's value and commitment to intellectual pursuits. Increased parental and familial involvement in a child's education improves communication between parents and teachers regarding the child's progress, needs, and concerns. This communication aims to enhance teachers' comprehension of their students and customize their teaching methods to cater to their requirements. Engaged parents are more likely to support education at the community and policy levels. This advocacy can help schools and communities provide the resources and support students need to succeed.

Respondents two and three (R2, R3) included community engagement. Collaboration between teachers and local community organizations can enhance students' educational experience by offering supplementary resources and assistance, including after-school programs, tutoring, and mentoring. Providing resources to students who lack access to them at home can be beneficial. Teachers can facilitate the involvement of community members in classroom settings through various means, such as guest speakers, field trips, and other related activities. Integrating real-world experiences into classroom learning can offer students valuable insights and connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications.

Variables Influencing Teacher Turnover in Rural Schools

Fewer possibilities for professional growth, feelings of isolation and lack of support, lower pay and fewer benefits, longer commutes, a less diverse student body, and fewer resources all play a role in keeping teachers from staying in rural schools. Ultimately, these factors can lead to teacher fatigue, discontent, and dissatisfaction in the workplace.

In the data gathered, respondent one (R1) was influenced by transportation, compensation, and benefits. Teachers working in schools in remote places need help getting to and from their schools. The fact that teachers have to travel long distances to get to their schools is a cause for worry because it could cost them time and money. Teachers need help getting to work in rural areas because there needs to be better public transportation. Fixing transportation problems for teachers in hinterland schools is essential because it's challenging to find and keep highly qualified teachers committed to giving students in these places a good education. Compensation and benefits also have an impact on rural teacher turnover. Due to lower pay and fewer benefits, rural schools may have difficulty attracting and retaining qualified educators. Low income and benefits can irritate, dissatisfy, and ultimately exhaust teachers. Teachers in rural areas may depart for higher wages or benefits. Improved compensation and benefits for rural instructors can attract and retain highly qualified educators, enhancing student outcomes and educational systems in remote areas.

Respondents two, three, and four (R2, R3, R4) were influenced by the classroom environment. In rural schools, teacher turnover is often higher due to the classroom setting. Teachers in rural schools need more resources, making it harder to foster a positive learning environment for their students. As a result, teachers may need help to give their students the individualized attention and materials they require. In addition, the demographics of their student bodies, such as a disproportionately large number of children from low-income families or students with impairments, may present additional difficulties for rural schools. Teachers' work satisfaction and retention can be increased by cultivating a welcoming and supportive learning environment. Teachers can better foster an environment conducive to learning and growth for their students if they have access to professional development opportunities, helpful materials, and mentoring programs.

Figure 2. Emergent Themes on Interactions with Seasonal Residents

Teacher's Different Approaches

The third aspect of the inquiry pertains to the instructional techniques employed by the teacher and their impact on student participation.

Three categories were created for overcoming challenges to provide valuable learning experiences for the students (Q1), two for methods and techniques to encourage students to become more involved in their learning (Q2), and only one for how the methods or techniques align with the needs and characteristics of the students (Q3). Three major themes emerged in the survey's third part: combating challenges for better educational opportunities for students, approaches to increasing student engagement and harmonizing pedagogical approaches with individual learner profiles.

Combating Challenges for Better Educational Opportunities for Students

Education for all children, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographical location, is a fundamental human right. Therefore, educators must acknowledge and tackle the distinct challenges encountered by students attending schools in remote areas. The presence of obstacles may hinder academic performance and potential. The pursuit of a more equitable educational system that promotes every child's cognitive and emotional development can be advanced through educators' resolution of these concerns.

Respondents one, three, and four (R1, R3, R4) said that personal well-being is essential in combatting challenges for better student educational opportunities. Putting teachers' emotional, mental, and physical well-being first can lead to more effectively meeting the needs of children and establishing an optimal learning environment. Promoting self-care and well-being in the classroom is most effective when teachers prioritize their health and well-being. Self-care prioritization among teachers can mitigate the risk of burnout and compassion fatigue, ultimately enhancing their ability to support their students effectively. Focusing on personal growth and development can enhance teachers' capacity to assist their students in rural schools in overcoming challenges.

The significance of time management in enhancing educational opportunities for students is emphasized by respondent two (R2). Large class numbers, a culturally and linguistically varied student body, and a lack of resources like computers and aides are some of the difficulties teachers in rural areas face daily. Teachers who manage their time well can provide a more stimulating and positive classroom environment for their students. Teachers can better assist their student's growth and development by planning and arranging their time to suit their needs through meaningful and engaging instruction. Teachers can avoid burnout and care for their health by properly balancing their work and personal lives, both facilitated by efficient time management. Therefore, time management is crucial

for educators to overcome obstacles and boost educational chances for students in rural schools.

R3 and R4 concurred that providing students with differentiated instruction could improve their access to quality education. In a diverse classroom, teachers are faced with the complex responsibility of catering to their student's unique needs, strengths, and learning styles, which can be challenging and fulfilling. Implementing differentiated instruction in the classroom enables educators to efficiently respond to the various demands of their students by modifying their teaching methods, materials, and assessments to align with the student's particular level of proficiency and understanding. Differentiated instruction by teachers can facilitate students' academic growth and development, prepare them for academic success, and enable the involvement of all children in the learning process. The delivery of differentiated lessons accommodates diverse learning styles, fosters student autonomy, and equips them with lifelong learning skills and strategies.

Table 3. *Teacher's Different Approaches*

	<i>Overcoming challenges to provide valuable learning experiences for the students (Q1)</i>	<i>Methods and techniques used to encourage students to become more involved in their learning (Q2)</i>	<i>How the methods or techniques align with the needs and characteristics of the students (Q3)</i>	<i>Themes</i>
				Combating Challenges for Better Educational Opportunities for Students
R1	Personal Well-being	Rewards and Punishment	Interests	Approaches for Increasing Student Engagement
				Harmonization of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles
				Combating Challenges for Better Educational Opportunities for Students
R2	Time Management	Rewards and Punishment	Interests	Approaches for Increasing Student Engagement
				Harmonization of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles
				Combating Challenges for Better Educational Opportunities for Students
R3	Personal Well-being Differentiated Instruction	Rewards and Punishment	Interests	Approaches for Increasing Student Engagement
				Harmonization of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles
				Combating Challenges for Better Educational Opportunities for Students
R4	Differentiated Instruction Personal Well-being	Discovery Learning	Interests	Approaches for Increasing Student Engagement
				Harmonization of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles

Approaches for Increasing Student Engagement

The engagement of students can be enhanced through the implementation of active learning strategies by teachers. Providing teacher feedback is instrumental in facilitating the learning process of pupils. The utilization of technology by teachers can enhance student engagement in diverse learning experiences. Solid and respectful interactions between teachers and students must establish a safe and supportive classroom environment that values and appreciates all children. Specific strategies can enhance student engagement, academic achievement, and personal development.

R1, R2, and R3 used punishment and rewards systems to encourage student participation in their class. When pupils are inspired to learn, they succeed. Schools' incentive and punishment systems vary widely, but they all share a fundamental goal: encouraging students to study. An efficient reward and punishment system is crucial to fostering an atmosphere conducive to teaching and learning.

Although schools' reward and punishment schemes are linked to a positive discipline strategy, the focus appears to be on punishment for misbehavior rather than improving students' engagement and motivation (Ching, 2012). Theoretically, rewards motivate students to work harder and learn more. Additionally, the rewards and punishments will increase students' interest in a subject. Incentives encourage pupils to do their best. If appropriately implemented, reward and punishment positively affect students' motivation and performance (Sidin, 2021).

Meanwhile, R4 adopted discovery learning to increase student participation. By having students actively seek out and uncover new information, the discovery learning approach fosters both active participation and critical thinking. Students' scientific knowledge, enthusiasm for the subject, and engagement in class discussions improve when they engage in discovery-based learning activities. Discovery learning cultivates students' natural inquisitiveness and inventiveness by encouraging them to seek out and investigate unfamiliar ideas and draw connections between previously unrelated topics (Chen et al., 2016).

Harmonization of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles

Teachers can better engage, motivate, and assist student learning if they take the time to get to know their students' backgrounds, interests, and strengths. Academic success and student satisfaction with their education can be increased by tailoring instruction to each student's learning profile (Kiani et al., 2020). Teachers can make classrooms more welcoming and conducive to learning if they adapt their strategies to meet the requirements of each student. The educational playing field can be leveled, and all students can succeed by integrating pedagogical approaches with unique student profiles.

All four respondents (R1, R2, R3, and R4) who utilized various methods and strategies to encourage student involvement agreed that their students' interests match those techniques and approaches. Student engagement and learning outcomes can significantly improve when teachers tailor their methods to their students' passions. Students were more engaged and willing to study when teachers employed tactics related to their interests. Students who said they were very interested in the subject matter showed the most significant gains in knowledge. Greene et al. (2018) suggest that better learning outcomes can be achieved by creating a classroom atmosphere that is more student-centered and engaging.

Students' level of engagement substantially impacts the success of educators' chosen methods of instruction. Students in rural areas are more likely to succeed academically and be motivated to learn if teachers use methods centered on them and tailored to their interests. Educators want to create a welcoming and stimulating classroom setting that encourages student learning and development, and one way to do this is by incorporating students' interests into the curriculum. One way to combat educational disparities and promote fairness in rural schools is to implement more student-centered teaching methods (Zhao et al., 2019).

Figure 3. *Emergent Themes on Teacher's Different Approaches*

Conclusion

This study focuses on the experiences of teachers teaching in hinterland schools or sparsely populated areas. The researchers surveyed to identify the challenges and opportunities associated with teaching in these areas and to explore the factors that influence the roles

and responsibilities of teachers in rural classrooms.

School Culture that Fosters Student Inquiry

The findings revealed that teachers' perspectives on rural education are influenced by their social, personal, and professional experiences. Teachers in remote schools must manage their classroom environment, plan and deliver lessons, engage with the local community, and maintain professional development. The area's school setting, student intervention, and cultural norms determined the influences on teachers' roles and responsibilities in rural classrooms. Teaching in remote areas has challenges and opportunities, such as making a difference, building relationships, limited resources, student diversity, teacher lack, and distance and isolation.

Interactions with Seasonal Residents

The interaction between teachers and the community is crucial in supporting student learning. The collaborative efforts of teachers, parents, families, and local organizations can establish a conducive and stimulating educational setting that fosters academic achievement among students. Active parental and family engagement, community engagement, and integrating real-world experiences into classroom learning can offer students valuable insights and connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications. On the other hand, variables influencing teacher turnover in rural schools include fewer possibilities for professional growth, feelings of isolation and lack of support, lower pay and fewer benefits, longer commutes, a less diverse student body, and fewer resources. The data gathered from the survey also showed that transportation, compensation, and benefits were factors influencing rural teacher turnover. Improved compensation and benefits for rural instructors can attract and retain highly qualified educators, enhancing student outcomes and educational systems in remote areas. Moreover, the classroom environment, including the student body's need for more resources and demographics, may present additional difficulties for rural schools. Therefore, cultivating a welcoming and supportive learning environment and providing access to professional development opportunities, helpful materials, and mentoring programs can increase teachers' work satisfaction and retention.

Teacher's Different Approaches

The study revealed that personal well-being, time management, and differentiated instruction could improve access to quality education for students. Active learning strategies, teacher feedback, technology, and solid interactions between teachers and students could also enhance student engagement. The last Tailoring instruction to each student's learning profile could increase academic success and student satisfaction.

The study on teachers' narratives in the hinterland schools revealed a need for increased communication and collaboration between team members and a focus on developing a more positive and supportive team culture. Implementing regular feedback mechanisms and providing training opportunities could benefit individual and team growth.

In conclusion, the teachers could benefit from a more cohesive and supportive culture, emphasizing open communication and ongoing learning and development. By addressing these areas, the teachers in the hinterland schools can improve their overall performance and achieve greater success in their work.

Based on the results, the researchers recommend that schools in rural areas can create a conducive environment for student inquiry by integrating real-world experiences into classroom learning, actively engaging parents, families, and the local community, and offering students access to valuable insights and connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications. Rural schools must provide competitive compensation and benefits packages to attract and retain highly qualified educators. This can help enhance student outcomes and educational systems in remote areas. Cultivating a supportive learning environment and providing access to professional development opportunities, helpful materials, and mentoring programs can increase teachers' work satisfaction and retention. This can also help enhance the quality of education provided to students in rural areas. By tailoring instruction to each student's learning profile, teachers can increase academic success and student satisfaction. This can be achieved through differentiated instruction and other active learning strategies. Developing a more positive and supportive team culture in rural schools can improve communication and collaboration between team members. It can also create a focus on ongoing learning and development and provide regular feedback mechanisms to facilitate individual and team growth.

References

- Ando, K., Basileisco, J., Deniega, A., Gador, K., Geraldo, P. J., Gipulao, W. E. M., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). Learning without Learning in the New Normal: College Education Students Lived Experiences in Blended Learning Modality. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 455-464.
- Azano, A. P. (2011). The Possibility of Place: One Teacher's Use of Place-based Instruction for English Students in a Rural. *Journal of Research in Rural Education*, 26(10). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331260922_The_Possibility_of_Place_One_Teacher's_Use_of_Place-based_Instruction_for_English_Students_in_a_Rural_High_School
- Barrera, D. & Shear, L. (2017). The Impact of Physical Environment on Teacher Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 55(6), 662-678. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-08-2016-0093>

- Bastida, E. J. (2022). Pedagogical Struggles and Gaps in Language Literacy Enhancement: The Case of Indigenous People's Education Teachers in the Philippines. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1). <https://ijci.globets.org/index.php/IJCI/article/view/1166>
- Benkert, D. & Toma, E. (2018). The Relationship Between School Facilities and Teacher Turnover Rates: Implications for School Finance Policy. *Education Finance and Policy*, 3(4), 549-570. https://doi.org/10.1162/edfp_a_00239
- Best, M., MacGregor, D., & Down, B. (2017). Designing for Diverse Learning: Case Study of Place-based Learning in Design and Technologies Pre-service Teacher Education. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(3), 91-106. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2017v42n3.6>
- Cabello, C. A., Logos, J., Bonotan, A. M. (2022). Part-Time Instructors in the Higher Education Institutions: The Less, The Limited, The Left-over, and The Survivors. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 6202-6214.
- Cabello, C. A., & Bonotan, A. M. (2021). Designing and validating an instrument to assess the wellness of business process outsources' customer service associates. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(1), 1-11.
- Chen, G. M. & Starosta, W. J. (2000). Communication Theory and Cultural Hegemony: Toward an Integrated Perspective. 10(4), 383-407. Doi: 10.1111/j.1468-2885.2000.tb00187.x
- Chen, H.-Y., Daehler, K. R., & Wissinger, D. C. (2016). Exploration, Engagement, and Enactment in Science Education: Encouraging Preservice Teacher Participation through the Development of a Classroom Teaching Unit. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 27(6), 693-718. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2016.1245638>
- Ching, G. (2012). Looking into the Issues of Rewards and Punishment in Students. *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 1(2), 29-38. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gregory-Ching-2/publication/266890375_Looking_into_the_issues_of_rewards_and_punishment_in_students_Looking_into_the_issues_of_rewards_and_punishment_in_students/links/5469f69e0cf20dedafd35970/Looking-into-the-issues-of-rewards-and-punishment-in-students-Looking-into-the-issues-of-rewards-and-punishment-in-students.pdf
- De Lisser, T. N. & Wilkinson, C. (2020). Attitudes of Hinterland and Coastland Teachers Towards Guyanese Creole. *The Journal of Education and Humanities*, 3. https://www.academia.edu/62580428/Attitudes_of_Hinterland_and_Coastland_Teachers_towards_Guyanese_Creole
- Elfer, C. (2016). Place-based Education – A Review of Historical Precedents in Theory and Practice. https://getd.libs.uga.edu/pdfs/elfer_charles_j_201108_phd.pdf
- Flores, A., Mendez, K., Tampus, J., & Cabello, C. (2023). The lived experiences of TLE teachers in the private institutions using blended teaching modality in the new normal. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(3), 285-295.
- Gallego, A. J. F. (2022). Lived Experiences of Public-School Heads Assigned in Remote Areas. *EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Education Management*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra10576>
- Gantalao, N., Gantalao, R., Romeo, A., Torino, R., & Cabello, C. (2023). Identifying Obstacles in Facing the Full Face-To-Face Classes: A Qualitative Inquiry. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(3), 237-248.
- Gharavi, S. & Khaledian, M. (2019). School Facility Quality and Teacher Retention in Iran. 38(1-2). 41-54. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EF-01-2019-0003>
- Gist, C. D. & Lubinski, C. A. (2012). Building Relationships and Creating Partnerships for Rural Schools: A Research-Based Framework. *Journal of Research in Rural Education*, 27(9), 1-17. doi: 10.4148/jrre.27.1.1
- Goldring, E., Taie, S., & Riddles, M. (2013). Teacher Satisfaction and Retention: A Comparative Study Analysis of Urban and Suburban Schools. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 18(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10824669.2013.743970>
- Gruenewald, D. A. (2023). The Best of Both Worlds: A Critical Pedagogy of Place. *Educational Researcher*, 32(4), 3-12. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189x032004003>
- Hornbeck, J. & Conner, B. (2013). Rural Teacher Recruitment, Retention, and Development: A Report on Key Indicators from National Data Sources.
- Howley, A., Howley, M., Camper, C. M., & Perko, H. (2011). Pace-Based Education at Island Community School. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 42(4), 216-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2011.556682>
- Ingersoll, R. M. & Perda, (2010). Is the Supply of Mathematics and Science Teachers Sufficient? *American Educational Research Journal*, 81(2), 201-233. doi: 10.3102/0002831210368988
- Ingersoll, R. M. & Strong, M. (2011). The Impact of Induction and Mentoring Programs for Beginning Teachers: A Critical Review of the Research. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(2), 201-233. doi: 10.3102/0034654311403323
- Israel, A. L. (2012). Putting Geography Education into Place: What Geography Education Can Learn from Place-Based Education and Vice Versa. *The Journal of Geography*, 111(2), 76-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2011.583264>
- Kiani, R., Tahriri, A., Hedayati, N., & Papi, A. (2020). Harmonization Of Pedagogical Approaches with Individual Learner Profiles to Promote Academic Performance and Student Satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(2), 224-244.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520904852>

Lisondra, M. J. (2023). Multigrade Teachers' Lived Experiences in Hinterland Schools: Management Plan. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 13(8), 1-1.

McInerney, P., Smyth, J., & Down, B. (2011). "Coming to A Place Near You?" The Politics and Possibilities of a Critical Pedagogy of Place-based Education. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*. 39(1), 3-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866x.2010.540894>

Murray, N., Liddoccat, A. J., Zhen, G., & Mosavian, P. (2020). Constraints on Innovation in English Language Teaching in Hinterland Regions of China. *Language Teaching Research*. 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820979855>

Persaud, G. & Tiwari, A. (2019). The Experiences of Teachers in Guyana's Hinterland Schools. *Journal of Education and Development in the Caribbean*. 16(1), 128-147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1942775119836036>

Robiños, J. R., Dasig, J. P., & Mendoza, L. O. (2020). Learning and Sharing: Understanding Experiences in Teaching Indigenous Learners of Mindoro. *Social Science Research Network*. 2(2), 108-116. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj372>

Sidin, S. A. (2021). The Application of Reward and Punishment in Teaching Adolescents. Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210325.045>

Tinampay, F. (2023). Lived Experiences of Teachers in the Hinterland School: Management Plan. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 13(8), 1-1.

Villar, M. C. G., Filipinas, J. P., Villanueva, J. B., & Cabello, C. A. (2022). The transition, transformation, and adaptation from modular-printed instruction to limited face-to-face Classes: A phenomenology.

Wang, M. T. & Degol, J. L. (2016). Motivational Pathways to STEM Career Choices: Using Expectancy-Value Perspective to Understand Individual and Gender Differences in STEM Fields. *Development Review*. 40, 133-166. Doi: 10.1016/j.dr.2016.06.002

Webber, G. (2021). Terrain of Place-Based Education. *Brock Education Journal*. 30(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.26522/brocked.v30i1.777>

Yemini, M., Engel, L., & Simon, A. B. (2023). Place-based Education: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Educational Review*. 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2023.2177260>

Zandvliet, D. B. (2012). Development and Validation of the Place-Based Learning and Constructivist Environment Survey (PLACES). *Learning Environments Research*. 15(2), 125-140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-012-9110-x>

Zeichner, K. M. & Johnson, E. (2015). Teacher Education in and for Rural Places. *Journal of Research*. 30(7), 1-14.

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